

“NOFILOGIK YO‘NALISHLARDA CHET TILINI O‘QITISHNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI”

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ANDIJON DAVLAT PEDAGOGIKA INSTITUTI

+998 74 224 44 02

adpi@edu.uz

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3. <https://www.joincake.com/blog/rest-in-peace>
4. Yulduz Usmonova – “Otajon” qo‘shig‘i
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WEB-BASED AND SMART LIBRARY SERVICES ENHANCE THE LEARNING AND RESEARCH EXPERIENCE

*Musoeva Aziza Botirovna,
Samarkand state institute of foreign languages,
Associate professor (PhD),
Email: musoevab@uwec.edu*

Abstract. This article analysis the web-based library services which have become increasingly important in today's digital world, providing users with easy and convenient access to the accessibility of library resources and facilities. It also highlights the transformation of library services from traditional to more web-based services that enable convenient and accessible access to resources. This study examines the key features of web-based library services and their potential impact on information access, user satisfaction, and library operations. It offers the establishment of such library services in the context of Uzbekistan public universities.

Keywords: web-based, library, online database, user-friendly, research, accessibility, library resources, facilities, digital world.

Introduction. While working as a visiting scholar at the University of Wisconsin Eau Claire in the United States of America, the concepts presented in this article were developed. As a visiting scholar and FEP finalist, my aim was to acquire valuable insights through practical experiences in the United States. Throughout the academic year of 2024, I accumulated a range of experiences and insights that have influenced this paper, emphasizing the importance of web-based library services, especially in public universities in Uzbekistan.

Education is crucial for equipping the younger generation with the essential skills and knowledge needed to thrive in today's competitive global landscape. Currently, efforts to enhance the quality of education in Uzbekistan mostly center on educational reform. Thus, the quick implementation of web-based library services at universities in Uzbekistan is a crucial change.

Web-based library services have gained significant importance in the current digital era by providing convenient and effortless access to library facilities and resources for students, faculty, and staff. This is due to the fact that contemporary students are considered technologically versatile and have a tendency to learn and adjust to new technologies at a faster rate than their predecessors. The internet has revolutionized the way in which we obtain and consume information; therefore, libraries must also evolve to remain relevant in this evolving era. In contemporary times, online libraries are proliferating due to their enhanced usability, whereas traditional libraries are experiencing a decline in importance due to high demand. Numerous prestigious universities across the globe are currently developing these services, emphasizing the need to digitize library resources.

Diverse researchers have provided numerous definitions of digital libraries; they are services that are delivered to users in a variety of formats via computer networks and are accessible via library logins, which ensure the security of the users. These services may include access to online document delivery services, online subscriptions and purchases, e-

books, e-journals, e-magazines, e-newspapers, and e-government publications, among others. These modifications enhance the user experience and promote engagement in research and learning by offering services in multiple formats, with a particular emphasis on the format that has been most embraced by its users. Utilizing web-based library services allows individuals to conveniently search for and retrieve resources from any location and at any time, using any internet-connected device [1].

In recent years, the term "smart library services" has also gained widespread usage. Although smart library services and digital or web-based library services may be used interchangeably, they are distinct concepts. By integrating technological advancements including artificial intelligence, machine learning, and the Internet of Things, smart libraries optimize library operations, streamline processes, and furnish patrons with tailored suggestions [2].

Digital library services include Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), Document Delivery Services, Metadata, Online teaching, digital reference services, library retrieval system, and institutional repositories. An Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) has transformed the conventional way people access library materials. It offers an information retrieval interface that assists users in accessing and retrieving library materials via various access points. The shift from a library card catalog to the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) is a significant advancement in library and information services, particularly in the current digital era [3].

It is crucial to ensure equal opportunities for all library users. Recent advancements show that libraries are utilizing various tools such as Blogs, RSS, E-mail, Institutional repositories, SMS, Google Drive/Google Books, QR codes, Biometric gate registers, Library kiosks, Virtual tours, Mobile book alerts, Library portals, 5G services, Marketing and promotion, E-documents/E-journals, and more to enhance user experience.

Accessing online library services is crucial as they offer customers easy access to library materials, regardless of their location or physical abilities. They offer convenience by allowing users to access resources based on their preferences, ultimately saving time and effort. Utilizing online library services helps reduce costs by eliminating the necessity for physical space, staff, and materials. Improving the customer experience can be achieved by providing personalized services that meet specific needs. Nevertheless, online library services come with constraints like technical obstacles, disparities in digital access, restricted availability of tangible materials, user satisfaction and choice, and worries about privacy and security. It is important for libraries to consider these limitations and make sure to address them when creating and launching web-based services. Web-based library services are crucial for libraries to stay current and adapt to the evolving needs of their users. They provide various advantages and chances, and libraries need to keep investigating and coming up with new ideas in this field to better serve their communities [4].

Regarding the University of Wisconsin Eau Claire, it is evident that they possess highly effective library resources and services. Students and faculty can access the library, known as McIntyre Library, through the university website. Students, faculty, staff, and community members utilize the library for a range of purposes. This resource is highly valuable and can be accessed at UW-Eau Claire. The library offers a wide range of services including library floor maps, online forms, research tools like library search and databases, assistance through chat, email, phone, and text, course guides, special collections support, borrowing options, equipment checkout, computer access, printing and scanning services, study rooms, locker rentals, and more [5].

They offer essential links to various digital library services like Featured Collections, Interlibrary Loan (ILL), Digital Collections, Faculty Guide, Library Guides, Key Resources, Streaming Video, E-books & Audiobooks, News, CINAHL, Web of Science, Psychology Databases, JSTOR, Westlaw, and more. Users can conduct research and gain knowledge from diverse perspectives and engaging services [5].

Interlibrary Loan provides additional research opportunities for students and educators who are unable to locate specific resources. By reaching out to Interlibrary Loan, individuals can receive guidance on accessing sources from a network of interconnected libraries.

They also provide regular activities catering to various audiences, providing opportunities for people to learn and do research according to their own requirements. In addition to its physical collection, the library offers a Photography Room, Virtual Room, Podcast recording room, Musical instruments rooms, and several other resources to cater to learners comprehensively.

The research indicates that creating well-equipped, online and smart libraries and important as they are essential for improving research skills and promoting research competence of students, educators and researchers [6].

In summary, this article delves into the reasons for establishing the well-equipped, online and smart libraries in Uzbekistan and details the process of setting it up, drawing inspiration from effective university libraries that prioritize research quality. The primary objective of establishing this type of library is to enhance education in Uzbekistan across all academic fields. The web-based digital libraries at universities in Uzbekistan strives to remedy the absence of research excellence and foster research in all fields. It aims to provide researchers, teachers, and instructors with necessary skills and knowledge.

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USING WEB-QUEST TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Ermirzayev Abbas Vaxobjonovich
Namangan state Institute of foreign languages
ermirzayev89@mail.ru

Annotatsiya: Maqolada o'quv jarayonida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish muammolari keltirilgan. Web-kvest texnologiyasidan foydalanish talabalarning mustaqil ishlashga bo'lgan munosabatini o'zgartirish, kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish (axborotni qidirish, tahlil qilish va baholash, jamoada ishlash).

Kalit so'zlar: Web-kvest, talabalarning mustaqil ishi.

The term “Web-Quest” was first proposed in the summer of 1995 by Bernie Dodge, a professor of educational technology at the University of San Diego (USA). The author

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